

Table of data.

Data type	Event	File name
Acoustic Emission data	E ₂	HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch1-ch4-E2-T2307-2337.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch5-ch8-E2-T2307-2337.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch9-ch12-E2-T2307-2337.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch13-ch16-E2-T2307-2337.csv
	E ₃	HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch1-ch4-E3-T2470-2502.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch5-ch8-E3-T2470-2502.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch9-ch12-E3-T2470-2502.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch13-ch16-E3-T2470-2502.csv
	E ₄	HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch1-ch4-E4-T2567-2667.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch5-ch8-E4-T2567-2667.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch9-ch12-E4-T2567-2667.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch13-ch16-E4-T2567-2667.csv
	E _e	HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch1-ch4-Ee-T8917-8947.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch5-ch8-Ee-T8917-8947.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch9-ch12-Ee-T8917-8947.csv
		HBR-15-06_AeWav-ch13-ch16-Ee-T8917-8947.csv
Fault slip	E ₄	FaultSlip.upload